

1 **Innate immune activation in TNBC cells resistance to chemotherapy.**

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8 Innate immune activation observed included induction of *TLR4* and *NLRP6*. CD4 activation appeared to
9 function in an adjuvant-type role. Prominent *IL-1* and *IL-6* pathway activation was also observed. *TNF* and
10 *LTB* were both silenced.

11 Citations

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